

Fuel Consumption Prediction Of Cars Using Machine Learning: A Comparitive Study

Swathy Krishna P R
Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College Of Engineering
Kanjirappally, India
swathykrishnapr2022b@mca.ajce.in

Rini Kurian
Asst.Professor in Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College Of Engineering
Kanjirappally, India
rinikurian@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract— Improving vehicle fuel economy necessitates the capacity to model and predict fuel efficiency. In this paper, the three Machine Learning models are used to compare fuel efficiency of cars for a large dataset. Linear regression, decision tree and random forest models have been used for the purpose and performance of the cars compared. The model could also help road managers better understand how much road vehicles utilize fuel and how road geometry affects their performance. The study also reveals that all three methods allow for the development of high-performing models, with the decision tree model marginally outperforming linear regression and random forest in terms of R2 and lower MSE value.

Keywords—Machine Learning, Linear Regression, Decision Tree, Random Forest.

I. INTRODUCTION

Predicting the fuel efficiency of cars is an important and interesting problem. This paper's major goal is to predict a car's performance based on fuel consumption in order to optimise a specific vehicle behaviour. This has the potential to dramatically improve the vehicle's efficiency. The car's performance is evaluated based on the engine type, number of cylinders, fuel type, and horsepower, among other factors. These are the features on which the efficiency of the car can be predicted. It is a continuous process of gathering, studying, analysing, and recording information about car's efficiency based on the characteristics listed above. Mileage, dependability, flexibility, and affordability are all performance objectives that can be paired together to help the prediction engine and engine management system. This method is crucial for understanding the vehicle's performance.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Hlasny et al. [1] looked into how driver behaviour, road conditions, weather, and traffic affect heavy-duty vehicle fuel usage. They discovered that altering driving behaviour before and during driving based on these parameters can minimise fuel usage. Following a review of the literature, it was discovered that few research have been published that describe the factors that influence truck fuel usage. As a result, other models' important research was also discussed in this section.

Li et al. [2] investigated the association between fuel consumption efficiency and driver characteristics using 10 month long-term data gathered by Toyota private cars. They discovered that some factors have a large impact on car fuel usage, while others have a minimal impact.

Chen et al. [3] built a fuel consumption forecast model that took into account previously unconsidered elements including the number of lanes and free-flow speed. The study's findings revealed that these factors takes an important role on motor vehicle fuel usage.

Ericsson et al.[4] developed independent measurements to define the characteristics of driving patterns and to determine which features have the greatest impact on emissions and fuel consumption. For each of the 19 230 driving patterns gathered in traffic, 62 driving pattern parameters were determined.

J. Wang and Rakha [5] developed a heavy-duty truck fuel prediction model based on a certain fuel consuming mmodel and calibrated it using field test data. The findings revealed that this model's prediction accuracy was superior to that of CMEM.

III. METHODOLOGY

Machine learning is an evolving technology that helps computers to automatically learn from past data. A machine learning system learns from previous data, builds prediction models, and predicts the outcome when new data is received. The amount of data aids in the construction of a better model that more precisely predicts the output; thus, the accuracy of anticipated output is influenced by the amount of data.

In this system, we area using three machine learning algorithms.

1. a. Decision Tree

The Decision Tree is a supervised learning technique that may be used in both classification and regression problems, however it is most commonly employed to address classification issues. Internal nodes represent dataset attributes, branches represent decision rules, and each leaf node offers the conclusion in this tree-structured classifier. To make judgements or execute tests, the features of the given dataset are utilised.

DOI:

ISBN: 978-93-5607-317-3@2022 MCA, Amal Jyothi College of Engineering Kanjirappally, Kottayam

2. b. Linear Regression

Linear regression is one of the most basic and extensively used Machine Learning algorithm. It's a statistical technique for performing predictive analysis. A linear relationship between a dependent (y) variable and one or more independent (x) variables is shown by the linear regression technique. It indicates a linear relationship and shows how the dependent variable's value changes as the independent variable's value changes.

3. c. Random Forest

A supervised learning method is used by Random Forest, a well-known machine learning algorithm. Random Forest is a classifier that averages the results of numerous decision trees applied to different subsets of a dataset to increase the projected accuracy of the dataset. The random forest, rather than depending on a single decision tree, uses the projections of each tree to anticipate the final output based on the majority of votes.

IV. DATASET

The prediction of fuel efficiency is based on a set of data. The dataset includes 398 variables in all. Among the vehicle dataset in the study which contain 7 features. The features of the cars given in the dataset is cylinders, displacement, horsepower, weight, acceleration, model year, origin. The dataset is divided into two training and testing data sets. The amount of data aims the construction of a better model that more precisely predicts the output; thus, the accuracy of anticipated output is influenced by the amount of data.

	mpg	cylinders	displacement	horsepower	weight	acceleration	model year	origin	car name
1	18.0	8	307.0	130	3504	12.0	70	1	chevrolet chevelle malibu
2	15.0	8	350.0	165	3693	11.5	70	1	buick skylark 320
3	18.0	8	318.0	150	3436	11.0	70	1	plymouth satellite
4	16.0	8	304.0	150	3433	12.0	70	1	amc rebel sst
5	17.0	8	302.0	140	3449	10.5	70	1	ford torino
6	15.0	8	429.0	198	4341	10.0	70	1	ford galaxie 500
7	15.0	8	454.0	220	4354	9.0	70	1	chevrolet impala
8	14.0	8	440.0	215	4312	8.5	70	1	plymouth fury iii
9	14.0	8	455.0	225	4425	10.0	70	1	pontiac catalina
10	15.0	8	390.0	190	3850	8.5	70	1	amc ambassador dpl
11	15.0	8	383.0	170	3563	10.0	70	1	dodge challenger se
12	14.0	8	340.0	160	3609	8.0	70	1	plymouth cuda 340
13	15.0	8	400.0	150	3761	9.5	70	1	chevrolet monte carlo
14	14.0	8	455.0	225	3086	10.0	70	1	buick estate wagon (sw)
15	24.0	4	113.0	95	2372	15.0	70	3	toyota corona mark ii
16	22.0	6	198.0	95	2833	15.0	70	1	plymouth duster
17	18.0	6	199.0	97	2774	15.0	70	1	amc hornet
18	21.0	6	200.0	85	2587	16.0	70	1	ford maverick
19	22.0	4	97.0	88	2130	14.0	70	3	datsun pl510
20	26.0	4	97.0	46	1835	20.0	70	2	volkswagen 1131 deluxe sedan
21	25.0	4	110.0	87	2072	17.0	70	2	peugeot 504
22	24.0	4	107.0	90	2430	14.0	70	2	audi 100 ls
23	25.0	4	104.0	95	2375	17.0	70	2	saab 99e
24	26.0	4	121.0	113	2294	12.0	70	2	bmw 2002
25	21.0	6	199.0	90	2648	15.0	70	1	amc gremlin
26	10.0	8	360.0	215	4615	14.0	70	1	ford f250
27									

Fig.1. Dataset for fuel efficiency prediction

V. IMPLEMENTAION

In this prediction system, we use the platform- jupyter that makes it easy to set up, access.

Initially, open jupyter notebook by using jupyter notebook command in cmd. Then create a new python file. After that, perform the following steps.

Step 1: Import Necessary Packages.

```
In [7]: import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import seaborn as sns
import statsmodels.formula.api as smf
```

Fig.2.Package importing

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6785538

ISBN: 978-93-5607-317-3@2022 MCA, Amal Jyothi College of Engineering Kanjirappally, Kottayam

Step 2: Add data in the Dataframe

```
In [8]: dataset=pd.read_csv('E:\Seminan\Fuel_Efficiency_Prediction\car_performance.csv')
dataset

Out[8]:
```

	mpg	cylinders	displacement	horsepower	weight	acceleration	model year	origin	car name
0	18.0	8	307.0	130	3504	12.0	70	1	chevrolet chevelle malibu
1	15.0	8	350.0	165	3693	11.5	70	1	buick skylark 320
2	18.0	8	318.0	150	3436	11.0	70	1	plymouth satellite
3	16.0	8	304.0	150	3433	12.0	70	1	amc rebel sst
4	17.0	8	302.0	140	3449	10.5	70	1	ford torino
...
393	27.0	4	140.0	85	2790	15.6	82	1	ford mustang gl
394	44.0	4	97.0	52	2130	24.6	82	2	vw pickup
395	32.0	4	135.0	84	2295	11.6	82	1	dodge rampage
396	28.0	4	120.0	79	2625	18.6	82	1	ford ranger
397	31.0	4	119.0	82	2720	19.4	82	1	chevy s-10

Fig.3. Imported dataset

Step 3: Then find the pairwise correlation of all columns in the dataframe and visualize the data

```
In [17]: corr_table=dataset.corr()
corr_table

Out[17]:
```

	mpg	cylinders	displacement	weight	acceleration	model year	origin
mpg	1.000000	-0.775396	-0.804203	-0.831741	0.420289	0.579267	0.563450
cylinders	-0.775396	1.000000	0.950721	0.896017	-0.505419	-0.348746	-0.562543
displacement	-0.804203	0.950721	1.000000	0.932824	-0.543684	-0.370164	-0.609409
weight	-0.831741	0.896017	0.932824	1.000000	-0.417457	-0.309564	-0.581024
acceleration	0.420289	-0.505419	-0.543684	-0.417457	1.000000	0.288137	0.205873
model year	0.579267	-0.348746	-0.370164	-0.309564	0.288137	1.000000	0.180662
origin	0.563450	-0.562543	-0.609409	-0.581024	0.205873	0.180662	1.000000

Fig.4.Correlation of data

```
In [18]: sns.heatmap(dataset.corr(),annot=True,linecolor='black', linewidths = 1)#
fig=plt.gcf()
fig.set_size_inches(8,8)
```

Fig.5. Data Visualization

Step 5: After that splitting the dataset into training and testing data.

```
In [50]: from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split

In [51]: x_train,x_test,y_train,y_test=train_test_split(x,y,test_size=0.1,random_state=0)
```

Fig.6. Splitting data

Step 6: Then 3 machine learning models have been developed to compare and predict fuel consumption of a vehicle. A statistical measure of how near the data are to the fitted regression line is R-squared.

$$\text{R-squared} = \frac{\text{Explained variation}}{\text{Total variation}}$$

The average of the squares of errors, which means the difference between the actual value (y) and the estimated value () is measured by the Mean Squared Error(MSE).

Based on higher R-squared and smallest MSE, we will decide which algorithm is best to predict fuel efficiency from the given dataset.

A. Decision Tree Regressor

```
In [52]: from sklearn.tree import DecisionTreeRegressor
dt=DecisionTreeRegressor(random_state=0,criterion="mae")
dt.fit(x_train,y_train)

In [47]: y_pred=dt.predict(x_test)
y_pred

Out[47]: array([[15. , 26.5, 14. , 19. , 18. , 31. , 31.8, 22. , 15. , 24.2, 36. ,
31.8, 18. , 26. , 15.5, 29. , 27. , 26. , 16. , 44. , 16. , 23. ,
25. , 19. , 34.2, 24.2, 29.8, 36. , 34.5, 15. , 19.2, 23.7, 18. ,
32. , 19.1, 23. , 19.4, 16. , 29. , 12. ]])

In [48]: y_test

Out[48]: array([[14. ],
[25. ],
[13. ],
[21. ],
[18. ]])
```

Fig.7. Importing Packages

```
In [58]: from sklearn.metrics import r2_score,mean_squared_error

In [59]: r2_score(y_test,y_pred)

Out[59]: 0.912578781275149

In [60]: mean_squared_error(y_test,y_pred)

Out[60]: 6.042499999999999

In [61]: np.sqrt(mean_squared_error(y_test,y_pred))

Out[61]: 2.458149710656371
```

Fig.8. R-squared and MSE

B. Random Forest Regressor

```
In [60]: from sklearn.ensemble import RandomForestRegressor

In [61]: rf= RandomForestRegressor(n_estimators=10,random_state=0,criterion='mae')
rf.fit(x_train,y_train)

In [62]: y_pred2=rf.predict(x_test)
y_pred2

Out[62]: array([[14.05, 25.55, 13.7 , 21.2 , 18.5 , 30.8 , 34.31, 22.5 , 15.1 ,
24.46, 32.01, 39.79, 17.8 , 24.85, 15.85, 31.31, 28.32, 26.93,
16.54, 32.12, 16.05, 25.6 , 23.86, 20.56, 32.19, 24.75, 32.39,
32.64, 31.02, 16.39, 18.35, 30.1 , 17.67, 31. , 22.91, 23.5 ,
19.77, 16.1 , 33.65, 12. ]])
```

Fig.9.Importing Packages

```
In [66]: from sklearn.metrics import r2_score,mean_squared_error

In [67]: r2_score(y_test,y_pred2)

Out[67]: 0.9013457876319049

In [68]: mean_squared_error(y_test,y_pred2)

Out[68]: 6.818917500000002

In [69]: np.sqrt(mean_squared_error(y_test,y_pred2))

Out[69]: 2.611305707878724
```

Fig.10. R-squared and MSE

C. Linear Regression

```
In [64]: from sklearn.linear_model import LinearRegression
mr=LinearRegression()
mr.fit(x_train,y_train)

In [71]: y_pred3=mr.predict(x_test)
y_pred3

Out[71]: array([[13.20818031],
[24.27993342],
[11.61339788],
[20.96914745],
[17.7247275 ],
[29.44595217],
```

Fig.11. Importing Packages

```
In [73]: from sklearn.metrics import r2_score,mean_squared_error
r2_score(y_test,y_pred3)

Out[73]: 0.846044380252153

In [74]: mean_squared_error(y_test,y_pred3)

Out[74]: 10.64131621470884

In [75]: np.sqrt(mean_squared_error(y_test,y_pred3))

Out[75]: 3.2621030355751857
```

Fig.12. R-squared and MSE

VI. RESULT

Three machine learning techniques were studied, three models were created, and their results were compared. These are Decision Tree Regressor, a Random Forest (RF), and Linear Regression.

The model with the higher R-squared value is a better fit for the data when comparing models. The model with the lower MSE value is a better fit for the data when comparing models.

Results of the analysis showed that in the view of predictions, from the comparison of the RMSE, MSE, and R2, DT is the model that gives the best performance, and is true for both cross-validation and testing sets.

EFFICIENCY FOR THE RF, LR, DT MODELS.

Model	RMSE	MSE	R2
Decision Tree	2.45	6.04	0.91
Random Forest	2.61	6.81	0.90

Linear Regression	3.26	10.64	0.84
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Fig.13.Fuel Efficiency Form

Fig.14.Fuel Prediction

VII. CONCLUSION

Three machine learning prediction models are evaluated in terms of their ability to predict a car's fuel consumption. Model which has higher R-squared and smallest error value is best to predict efficiency. We are a building a model to predict the fuel efficiency. To improve the forecasting abilities even more, we want to incorporate more factors influencing fuel use such as traffic, weather in future work. We're also working on a module that will walk you through the process of reengineering your processes to save money on gas by improving fleet scheduling and driving patterns.

2. VIII. REFERENCE

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